

Documentation

Survey

A correction flag of the SoSciSurvey questionnaire is available under "Survey". There you can find all used pages incl. php-code for randomizations etc.

The original articles containing the used scales are not included in the materials due to copyright concerns.

Data sets

The data sets are stored under "Data". The individual files contain the following data sets:

- **data_complete.xlsx** = All collected data including the excluded data sets. Note: In the column "Exclusion" the reason for the exclusion of the data set is noted.
- **data.xlsx** = Data set used for analysis (includes all intervention groups)
- **data_BAO.xlsx** = data set of BAO-group used for analysis
- **data_BAP.xlsx** = data set used of BAP-group for analysis
- **data_control.xlsx** = data set of controlgroup used for analysis
- **Coded_WritingTask_A.pdf** = contents of the writing tasks, coded by coder A, includes coding guide

Codebook

The codebook in which all variables are detailed has been uploaded with the name "Codebook". It contains variable names (as used in the data sets), variable labels (short description or item text), response codes, response values and variable type for the surveyed variables. Variable names appear in the order of the xlsx-table of the data sets from left to right.

Analytic Code in R

R and RStudio were used for the analysis. The code is stored under the file name "Analytic Code".

The code snippets appear in the order in which they were used in the analysis. For better orientation, the code elements are briefly commented.